

ECOLOGICAL CRISIS AND ITS IMPACT ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE OF KARAKALPAKISTAN RESIDENTS

Zholtaeva Madina Kipchakbaevna

Psychiatrist.

Karakalpak branch of the psychiatric service of the scientific and practical medical specialized center for mental health of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

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Abstract. *This article examines the problems of environmental impact on the mental state of the population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The author also examines the definitions of scientists about the mental health of the population, and provides definitions of the WHO.*

Keywords: *psychological state of the residents of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, environmental conditions, socio-economic problems, problems of psychiatric services.*

ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ КРИЗИС И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ЖИТЕЛЕЙ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы влияния окружающей среды на психическое состояние населения Республики Каракалпакстан. Автор также рассматривает определения ученых о психическом здоровье населения, приводит определения ВОЗ.*

Ключевые слова: *психологическое состояние жителей Республики Каракалпакстан, экологические условия, социально-экономические проблемы, проблемы психиатрической службы.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Complex environmental conditions, large-scale migration of the population abroad and socio-economic problems caused by modern transformations of society, revaluation of values with a pronounced prevalence of material over spiritual, problems in personnel and management policies make the study of the psychological state of the residents of the Republic of Karakalpakstan even more relevant.

In connection with the extremely little study of the problem of psychiatric services in general and socio-psychological, regional aspects in particular, it is necessary to give definitions of some scientists that fully justify the relevance of the study of this problem: "Mental health of the population is a state of mental well-being, characterized by the absence of painful mental

manifestations and ensuring adequate regulation of behavior to the conditions of the surrounding reality”.[4]

In recent years, significant efforts have been made in Uzbekistan to improve mental health care and rehabilitation of the population. In 2019, the Concept for the Development of Mental Health Services for the Population for 2019-2025 was approved.[8] This concept is aimed at improving the quality of psychiatric care, introducing advanced diagnostic and treatment technologies, and combating stigmatization and discrimination against people with mental disorders.

This resolution sets a number of tasks for the psychiatric service in order to further develop the system of mental health protection for the population, organize the provision of high-quality psychiatric care, prevention, diagnosis and treatment of mental disorders in the republic, which implement the seven goals recommended by the WHO.[2] These goals are aimed at creating a more accessible, high-quality and equitable mental health care system.

II. MAIN PART

In 2001, WHO stated that for all people, mental, physical and social health are essential components of life that are closely interrelated. The WHO Constitution (1946) defines health as “a state of complete mental, physical and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”.[1]

The state of human health is the result of the impact of a complex of various factors: genetic characteristics of the organism, lifestyle, social level, natural conditions of the environment. The study of the influence of various factors on the formation of health and their assessment are an integral part of medical and environmental research, since the aggravation of the socio-economic problems of the individual, society, and people in the Republic of Karakalpakstan further actualizes socio-psychological problems.

We agree with the opinion of some scientists who define health: “The analysis of mental and psychological levels of health, characteristic of psychology, psychiatry, valeology, is focused on the problem of the richness of personality development, personal growth, the desire for self-actualization and is devoted to the consideration of the structure of the personality and the factors that determine its health and well-being. The social level of analysis of the health category is associated, first of all, with the determination of social conditions that ensure the health of individuals, individual groups and public health, as well as with the disclosure of the concepts of social status, social well-being, and social security”.[3]

For example, one of the social problems that is directly related to the economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the material well-being of the Karakalpak

people is the rather pronounced migration of the population. The pronounced intercountry migration of the predominantly male population of young and mature age gives rise to:

- deterioration of the material well-being of the family;
- decrease in the birth rate;
- real growth of single-parent families in legally registered marriages;
- increase in the number of sexually unsatisfied women of childbearing age with their historical independence and relatively free inter-gender communication;
- disproportion of the sexes, a sharp increase in extramarital affairs and weakening of the institution of the family;
- consigning to oblivion a number of valuable folk traditions;
- a tendency of population aging with insufficient socio-economic development of the country. This leads to an increase in socio-economically vulnerable elderly people;
- gradual decrease of the Karakalpak ethnic group with all its irreparable psychogenetic, cultural-historical, socio-demographic consequences.[9]

Of course, economic difficulties can be observed from time to time in most people and they can often play an educational role. But when they are systematic and are observed in combination with constant stress in the family or at work, the risk of psychological illnesses increases sharply.

"Mental health is the state of an individual, which is characterized by the integrity and consistency of all mental functions of the body, providing a feeling of subjective mental comfort, the ability for purposeful meaningful activity, adequate (taking into account ethnocultural criteria) forms of behavior".[6]

Another almost always unnoticed factor is ecology. This is the chemical composition of water, soil, air. This is increased radiation, which affects humans and, above all, the psyche, causing depression. DDT, which is completely harmless, in the opinion of an ordinary person who does not know its effect on the human body, and therefore is so widely used by every family to fight insects, the so-called "dust" among the people, does not disintegrate for decades, does not lose its particularly dangerous effects on the human body. It is not broken down by temperature, moisture, or rays. It can enter the body through water, plants, vegetables, air, meat and other agricultural products.[7]

Pesticide DDT causes autism. Scientists have proven that high concentrations of DDT in the bodies of expectant mothers sharply increase the risk of giving birth to children with autism.

This is the conclusion reached by American medical scientists who published an article in the "American Journal of Psychology".[5]

Research conducted by Columbia University scientists over 60 years has shown that

women develop breast cancer 40 years after exposure to DDT.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

These chemicals, widely used in agriculture and in everyday life, primarily have a detrimental effect on the nervous system, on the functions of the brain, on the organs of internal secretion. Depression, a number of neuropsychiatric diseases, suicide attempts - all this is a derivative of the central nervous system, the brain. This means that in agriculture and in everyday life, due to ignorance of the harmful effects of chemicals, people have poisoned and continue to poison themselves, others and nature. It should be noted with regret that the instructions for use, storage and prevention of their harmful effects are not communicated at the proper level even to the workers using them, not to mention the people.

The discrepancy between the composition of the air, the chemical composition of drinking water, soil, plants, vegetables, food consumed, increased radiation in certain regions and their harmful effects on our body is an invisible powerful enemy that is much more dangerous than cholera, plague or corona virus.

The listed especially dangerous infections (plague, cholera, etc.), well known to the people, have their own specific pathogen, against which vaccines have been developed. And it is possible to isolate and take appropriate quarantine measures, which countries did with the corona virus.

However, nothing can be done without completely disrupting the ecology, which will manifest itself in the form of various diseases and shorten the lives of millions of people. We see this in the example of the Aral Sea, but unfortunately, we do not learn the lessons.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, it should be especially noted that a significant portion of mentally ill people are people who are victims of ecology. Economy and ecology are two leading factors in mental illnesses. For example, landscape-geochemical factors are among the natural factors that affect the health of the population of Karakalpakstan. Increased mineralization and pH of surface waters, high content of chlorides and sulfates in them increase the risk of developing diseases of the digestive organs. High ammonia content in natural waters is a risk factor in the occurrence and development of diseases of the circulatory system. Air pollution, high levels of chemicalization of agriculture, poor quality of drinking water and its general absence as such are anthropogenic factors that adversely affect health. Each of the studied factors in the total amount of their negative impact is expressed by a certain share contribution to the formation of environmental risks. The population of Karakalpakstan is characterized by a high level of malignant neoplasms. The dependence of the population morbidity rate on the content of chemical elements and their compounds in soils, waters, and air has also been revealed. The presence of nitrogen oxides, carbon

monoxide, and sulfur dioxide in the atmospheric air contributes to the development of pulmonary pathologies, genitourinary diseases, and congenital anomalies. Soil pollution with mineral fertilizers and pesticides affects the incidence of circulatory and genitourinary diseases. Low quality drinking water increases the risk of genitourinary diseases, digestive organs, and circulatory organs. Therefore, we believe that it is important to study the effects of such factors on human health in general and mental health in particular.

In connection with the above, we would like to present seven key areas identified by the World Health Organization (WHO) to improve mental health care and the mental health of the population:

“1. Strengthening leadership and management: Developing and implementing national strategies and action plans on mental health.

2. Ensuring the integration of mental health into primary health care: Training health workers and ensuring the availability of mental health care at the primary health care level.

3. Developing community mental health services: Creating and supporting services that provide care in the community, and not only in specialized institutions.

4. Improving access to psychiatric medications: Ensuring the availability and quality of psychiatric medications.

5. Reducing stigma and discrimination: Conducting information campaigns and educational programs to reduce the stigma of people with mental disorders.

6. Strengthening human rights: Ensuring respect for human rights in mental health care and protecting the rights of patients.

7. Monitoring and Evaluation: Developing monitoring and evaluation systems to track the progress and effectiveness of mental health programs".[2]

Let us reiterate that these goals are aimed at creating a more accessible, high-quality and equitable mental health care system.

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